

Pest management and control

WEEDS

Striga root parasite – a problem of dryland rice in the African savanna environment

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Striga species destroyed large tracts of rice in a commercial mechanized scheme for dryland rice at Sirasso, northern Ivory Coast, in October 1976. The most frequent species was *Striga forbesii*, with pink flowers; the least frequent was

S. hermonthica, with violet flowers.

Large areas of rice were killed by flowering time. There was a gradient where plants were progressively less affected between the killed areas and remnant areas of healthy rice. At the time of rice maturity, the *Striga* was flowering and vigorous in the fringe areas of stunted rice but it had already matured and died in the areas where the rice was destroyed earlier in the season. *Striga* plants beyond affected areas were rare.

All varieties being grown – Moroberekan, Iguape Cateto, IRAT 13 (irradiated short mutant of 63-83),

IRAT 8 (Moroberekan 63-105), IRAT 10 (Lung-Sheng 63-104), and a sister line of IRAT 10 - were affected equally.

Striga is a common problem on maize and sorghum in the savanna areas of Africa, and it has previously been casually noted on rice. It now appears that *Striga* is more than just a curiosity in rice and that it can destroy large areas if dryland rice cultivation expands in the savanna.

Mechanized cultivation with combine harvesters might extensively spread the parasite's very small seeds. Experiments are required to determine if control is possible through land management, crop rotation, or herbicides. The extensive area of severe infestation offers the possibility of screening for varietal differences in reaction to *Striga* to determine if rice resistance could be a means of control. **WY**

Soil and crop management

Effect of *Azolla* as a green manure crop on rice yields in northeastern Thailand

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Plants of *Azolla pinnata* were collected from a natural habitat in a swampy area in northeast Thailand in the 1977 wet season. They were multiplied in tanks until sufficient stock was produced to seed the experimental plots at an inoculation rate of 312 kg/ha before rice is transplanted. Several treatments were applied to accelerate the growth of *Azolla* in the experimental lots (see table).

Azolla was incorporated into the soil as a green manure at 29 days after inoculation. No *Azolla* was incorporated in the check treatment. The objectives were to find the best method of multiplying *Azolla* in rice fields and to compare the effects of *Azolla* as a green manure with those of chemical fertilizers

on the yield of the variety RD 1.

Azolla was remarkably effective; RD1's yield response to it was greater than its

response to 37.5 kg inorganic N/ha (see table, treatments 5 and 6).

The extremely sandy soil at the

Effect of *Azolla* on rice yields.

Treatment no.	Treatments		Fresh wt of <i>Azolla</i> before planting (kg/ha)	Paddy yield ^b (t/ha)
	<i>Azolla</i>	Fertilizer ^a (kg/ha)		
1	None	0-30-25	-	2.6 c
2	None	18.75-30-25	-	2.8 c
3	None	37.5-30-25	-	2.9 bc
4	<i>Azolla</i> grown without fertilizer, and incorporated before transplanting	0-30-25	794	2.9 bc
5	<i>Azolla</i> grown with 30 and 25 kg/ha P ₂ O ₅ and K ₂ O fertilizer as basal application and incorporated in soil	0-0-0	11,450	3.5 a
6	<i>Azolla</i> grown with 30 kg/ha, P ₂ O ₅ split 3 times at 10-day intervals then incorporated in soil	0-0-25	18,919	3.5 a
7	<i>Azolla</i> not incorporated in soil but 30 kg/ha P ₂ O ₅ , split 3 times at 10-day intervals	0-0-25	18,606	2.6 c

^aFertilizer applied to plot on day before transplanting.

^bValues followed by the same letter are not significantly different at 5% level.

^cNitrogen split equally between transplanting and panicle initiation stage.